

1 **CDKN status integrates the primitive state of the HSC (self-renewal) with intent for asymmetric cell**
2 **division (cycling).**

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7 We recently described *Cdkn1a* silencing in the hematopoietic stem cell (HSC). We report here multi-layer
8 CDKN activation repression which integrates the primitive state of the HSC (self-renewal) with intent for
9 asymmetric cell division (cycling).

10 LT-HSC from mice engineered to lack CD41, a platelet integrin that marks fetal and adult HSC, continue to
11 repress *CDKN1A* but activate *CDKN1C*. *CDKN2C* and *CDKN2B* were instead silenced during transition
12 from HSC to LT-HSC in mice. We demonstrate here clonal heterogeneity in the HSC signaled by CDKN
13 activation/repression which essentially captures integration of intent of the cell to cycle (entry to cell
14 division) and the primitive nature of the HSC cellular state which is characterized by self-renewal.

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